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ENERGY AUDIT, CONSERVATION AND POWER FACTOR

IMPROVEMENT FOR AEGIS Pvt. Ltd. GGN

Sandeep

M.Tech Scholar, Department of Electrical Engineering, Ganga Institute of Technology and Management, Jhajjar Haryana (India)

Er. Joginder Singh

Assistant Professor, Department of Electrical Engineering, Ganga Institute of Technology and Management, Jhajjar Haryana (India)

Abstract:

The main focus of this paper is to achieve and maintain optimum energy throughout the organization so as to minimize energy costs and improve power quality. Energy Audit is a systematic approach for decision-making in the area of energy management. A simple payback period calculation and formulation has been executed.

This paper report is aimed at “Managing Energy use in Aegis Pvt. Ltd Grogam”. It is a concerted attempt in achieving improved energy performances with a valid power factor limit. This study suggests different opportunities to create and implement an energy management plan in the building. The audit was conducted and suitable strategies of adjusting and optimizing energy were suggested so as to reduce energy requirements and hence, the total cost spent towards energy consumption.

Key Words: Energy Audit, Conservation, Energy Saving, Types of Auditing. Liquid-Crystal Display (LCD), Cathode Ray Tube (CRT), Kilowatt (KW), Kilo-volt-ampere (KVA), Kilovolt-ampere reactive (KVAR).

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Energy Audit

As per Indian Energy Conservation Act 2001, Energy Audit is defined as: “the verification, monitoring and analysis of use of energy including submission of technical report containing recommendations for improving energy efficiency with cost benefit analysis and an action plan to reduce energy consumption “. It is the basic and most important step for implementation of any effective energy management program. It provides an opportunity to look into energy use pattern and suggests way and mean of eliminating losses and improving the efficiency of the system. The immediate advantages obtained through energy audit are improved maintainability, reliability features coupled with reduction losses. Long term energy saving can be through the use of energy efficient equipment. [3]

Today world has reached a stage, where energy is becoming major cost factor in almost all processes in life. Also, in many organizations energy and profit are closely related that the financial and energy audits are totally interlinked. Most of the organizations are weak in keeping track of the energy spent and hence consuming more energy than what is required for optimum work. Energy audit distinctly addresses these programs. Any saving in

energy usage directly leads to the profitability of the organization. Hence for each organization it is necessary to pay more attention towards the energy saving opportunities available to them, through proper energy audit.

The objective of Energy Audit is to promote the idea of Energy Conservation in the building of AEGIS. The purpose of the energy audit is to identify, quantify, describe and prioritize cost saving measures relating to energy use in major apartment of the building. The main area for Energy Audit Study should be directed towards:

- Checkout the areas of higher energy use and estimation of energy saving potential in Floor, Fire Pump Room and Other Critical Area like server room, IT room etc.
- Suggesting cost-effective measures to improve the efficiency of energy use.
- Estimation of costs and payback period.
- Documenting results & information generated through these activities.
- Identifying the possible usages of co-generation, renewable sources of energy (like Solar Energy) and recommendations for implementation, wherever possible, with cost benefit analysis.

A. 1.2 Types of Energy Audit

Basically energy audit is classified into following categories:

- Preliminary energy audit
- Targeted Energy Audit
- Detailed energy audit

1) 1.2.1 Preliminary Audit

Preliminary energy audit can be obtained by data Establishes, the energy consumption in the building, Calculate the scope for saving, Identifies the most critical areas for attention, identifies areas for more detailed study, measurement Preliminary Audit is performed in a limited time period. It mainly deals with improved better operation practices, proper utilization of energy, avoiding losses and wastages. Preliminary audit focuses its attentions mainly on major energy supplies and demands, accounting at least for 75% of the total energy requirement in the system. It mostly involves the following steps:

- Forming a team with available in-house expensive.
- Carrying out walk through survey.
- Collecting system data pertaining to energy consumption, for last one/two year.
- Developing energy consumption profile according to the data collection.
- Surveying the energy used in non-working hours.
- Developing check list of normal working hours keeping the routine practices and functions.

1.2.2 Targeted Energy Audit

Targeted energy audits are mostly based upon the outcome of the preliminary audit results. They provide data and detailed analysis on specified target projects. As an example, an organization may target its lighting system or boiler system or compressed air system with a view to bring about energy savings. Targeted audits therefore involve detailed surveys of the target subjects/areas with analysis of the energy flows and costs associated with those targets.

2) 1.2.3 Detailed Audit

Detailed Energy Audit checkout all systems and equipment which consume energy and the audit comprises a detailed study on energy savings and costs. It includes engineering recommendations and well defined projects with priorities. Detailed audit generally includes long-term measures such as technology, equipment, control logic and major modifications in system etc. The recommendations are usually long-term projects ranging from three to five years. It accounts approximately to 95% of energy utilized in the system. It involves a detailed technical analysis of each individual equipment, process to

- Quantify energy consumption by actual measurements over a period of time.
- Carryout detailed studies for various options available to modify.
- Implement the changes and continuously monitor the effects so as counter check the reduction in consumption.
- Integrate with the observations of preliminary audits.

B. 1.3 Energy Audit Methodology

The methodology adopted for this audit is a three step process comprising of:

1. **Data Collection:** In preliminary data collection phase, exhaustive data collection was performed using different tools such as observation, interviewing key persons, and measurements with the help of Power analyzer.
2. **Data Analysis:** Detailed analysis of data collected was done by different ways like comparing with previous year data. And all database was used for producing graphical representations.
3. **Recommendation:** On the basis of results of data analysis and observations, some steps for reducing power consumption without affecting the comfort and satisfaction were recommended along with their cost analysis. [3]

C. 1.4 Analysis of Power Consumption

With the use of the software Elektra, we have analyzed the power consumption by equipment. Since All floor had the potential of maximum power conservation, hence equipment, application as well as location wise analysis of floor was done. Here is the summary of the analysis presented in form of charts for better understanding.

1) 1.4.1 Lighting Load

The Main Load of Aegis Building is of Lighting. The lighting sources in the building are running 24hr. (aprx). As there is the only BPO type work, which required a close surrounding area and need proper cooling. The floor wise analysis of the lighting load is as shown in graph.

Fig:01

As the data was collected during the month of April, it can be seen that cove light have 32%, transformer area have 0%, Outer area have 1%, upper basement and ground floor have 8% each, and all floor have 7% each share in power consumption. Terrace Lighting come into picture with a combination of 2% share. This is the equipment where power can be saved by replacing the CFL tublight with LED. The power consumed by LED monitors is approximately 1/3rd when compared to CFL. Further outer area, T/F area, Terrace lightning has 3% share and it was observed that these lights are not used during whole day as sufficient lightning is there, so during calculation it was assumed that these lightning is used only for 10 hours.

2) 1.4.2 PC Load

This block comprises of all type of PC load in the building.

Fig:02

The equipment wise analysis of this type of load suggests that Computers (LCD) are the maximum power consuming equipment with 61.37% of the total power consumption by the full PC set.

3) 1.4.3 AC Load

In the building the huge load is only due to a huge requirement for cooling system. In all the building temperature maintain only by different type of ac system like Split, VRV, Ductable, Precision AC unit. Split unit are used in Clint cabin. And Ductable & Precision AC unit are used for UPS Room and Server Room. In all over the building VRV unit are used. Due to which electricity consumption so high.

Fig:03

4) 1.4.4 Other Type of Load

Fig:04

The analysis of other type of load like jockey pump, hydrant pump, Sprinkler pump, Sump pump, Lift system, Exhaust fan etc are gave the different load consumption. All Fire system pump are remaining in auto mode 24hr. to maintain the fire line pressure constant. Different load consumption is shown by the above pie chart. All sump pump is used to drain waste water from basement area and w/c area. All these all used in daily routine. A huge load is increased by the 24hr use of 4no’s of Passenger lift system. In the building there are 30nos of exhaust used for fresh air system due to which consumption of electricity increase. All these type load is necessary for a building.

5) 1.4.5 Total Load

Below pie chart gives a brief detail of all type of load in the building with their percentage values. Total lighting load of the building is 13% of the full load of the building and AC load is main load in it which is more the half of full load. 10% load is due to all other building equipment which are used in daily routines and it is necessary to it.

Fig:05

D. 1.5 Power Factor Improvement

The power factor of an AC electrical power system is defined as the ratio of the real power flowing to the load, to the apparent power in the circuit. Apparent power is the product of the voltage and current of the circuit. In an electric power system, a load with low power factor draws more current than any other load with a high power factor. The higher currents drawn by the load increase the energy losses in the power distribution system, and require higher rating wires and other equipment. Because of the costs of larger equipment and wasted energy, electrical utilities will usually charge a higher cost to industrial or commercial customers where there is a low power factor. [2] If the power factor is low, for the same supply voltage & load current drawn will be higher with low power factor, higher current will result in higher Copper loss i.e. (I^2R) in cable & transmission wires and increasing the transmission losses. It is fact that electricity users relying on alternating current with the exception of heating elements - absorb from the network not only the active energy they convert into mechanical work, light, heat, etc. A low power factor increase the cost and the utility companies may charge additional fees when the power factor is less than 0.97. Induction motor efficiency can be improved by installing capacitor bank. Linear loads with low power factor (such as induction motors) can be corrected with a passive network of capacitors bank. Non-linear loads, like rectifiers, deform the current drawn from the system. In this type of cases, active or passive power factor correction may be used to subvert the distortion and raise the power factor value.

The approximate capacitor rating is shown in Table below

Motor nominal rating (KW)	Capacitor power rating (KVAR)
1 to 1.9	0.5
2 to 2.9	1.0
3 to 3.9	1.5
4 to 4.9	2.0
5 to 5.9	2.5
6 to 7.9	3.0
8 to 10.9	4.0
11 to 13.9	5.0
14 to 17.9	6.0
18 to 21.9	7.5
22 to 29.9	10.0
30 to 39.9	Approximately 40% of motor power
40 and above	Approximately 40% of motor power

Table:01

II. 2. RESULTS

2.1 Cost Analysis of Replacing CRT monitors with LCD monitors:

Total No. of computers with CRT monitors in Building = 3040.

Power saved per monitor = 250W

Total Power saving = 760kW

Average Use of computers per year = 270*4h = 1080h

Total Energy saved per year = 820800kWh

Saving in Rs. Per year = 820800*5.0 = Rs. 41,04,000\-

Average Cost of Replacing each Monitor isRs. 7000\-

Total Cost of Replacing all monitors is Rs. 21,280,000\-

Capital Cost Recovery time = 5.18yr.

Hence, the capital cost recovery time for replacing CRT monitors by LCD monitors is 5.18years. Since the product life is more than that, the move is economically beneficial.

2.2 Efficiency Comparison of Different Motors

Efficiency At Full Load	Slip Ring 3- Φ IM	Slip Ring 1- Φ IM
Before Improving Efficiency	71.41%	71.56%
After Improving Efficiency	76.36%	73.20%

Table:02

Fig:06

From the above graph it can be conclude that the efficiency can be improved by using power capacitor for AC machine. Also the cost and the payback analysis are calculated as shown

below[4]

2.3 Three Phase Induction Motor

- A 5hp 3 Φ slip ring induction motor has an efficiency of 71% at full load
The losses of motor=29%

Hence total losses for 3.7KW=1.073KW

- The total power supplied to the motor for one hour=3.9701KWh
- Assuming that motor is running 4 hours for a day, So for 1 month =120hrs
- The electricity bill rating of 3 Φ slip ring induction motor for industries is Rs 15/KWh
- The total units consumed in one month =476.412KWh
- The total running cost =7146.18 Rs

2.4 After Improving the Efficiency

- When the efficiency of 3 Φ slip ring induction motor is increased to 76% at full load. The losses in motor=24%

Hence total losses for $3.7\text{KW}=0.888\text{ KW}$

- The total power supplied to the motor for one hour= 3.2856KWh
- Assuming that the motor is running 4 hours for one day, So for one month= 120hrs
- The electricity bill rating of 3Φ slip ring induction motor for industries is $\text{Rs}15/\text{KWh}$
- The total units consumed in one month= 394.272KWh
- The total running cost = $\text{Rs }5914.08\text{-}$

III. 3. CONCLUSIONS

THIS AUDIT WAS CONDUCTED TO SEEK THE OPPORTUNITIES TO IMPROVE THE ENERGY EFFICIENCY OF THE CAMPUS. FOR SIMPLY IDENTIFYING THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION PATTERN, THIS AUDIT SOUGHT TO IDENTIFY THE MOST ENERGY EFFICIENT APPLIANCES AS WELL. MOREOVER, SOME DAILY PRACTICES RELATING COMMON APPLIANCES(I.E. PPM) HAVE BEEN PROVIDED WHICH MAY HELP REDUCING THE ENERGY CONSUMPTION.

3.1 General Observation

- Use day lighting as much as possible with proper ventilation.
- It has been observed that the operators fail to turn of the equipment when not in use. So it is suggested to create awareness among the people about the important of Energy Conservation.
- Use Energy Conservation slogans in the work area as this motivates them to conserve energy.

Following are few slogans which could be used to motivate people to conserve energy

1. Energy misused cannot be excused.
2. Save one unit a day, keep power cut away.
3. The less you burn the more you earn.
4. When sunlight is bright switch off the light.
5. Today's wastage is tomorrow's shortage.
6. Energy earns or simply burns, choice is yours.
7. A thing which burns never returns.
8. Manage energy well to avoid damage.
9. One unit of energy saved is two units of energy generated.
10. Energy is life conserve it.

REFERENCES

- [1] Guidelines for preparation of energy audit report. [http://www.beeindia.in/energy_manager_auditors/document/ea_em/Guidelines for preparation of audit report.pdf](http://www.beeindia.in/energy_manager_auditors/document/ea_em/Guidelines%20for%20preparation%20of%20audit%20report.pdf).
- [2] Power factor correction equipment, [http://www.ul.com/global / documents/offering/perspectives/regulators/technical /ul_power factor correction equipment.pdf](http://www.ul.com/global/documents/offering/perspectives/regulators/technical/ul_power_factor_correction_equipment.pdf).
- [3] Hand book on energy audit and environmental management – Y.P Abbi and Shashank Jain.
- [4] Power factor correction of 3Φ induction motor, [http://www.electrical-insulation.org/enwiki/power factor correction of induction motor](http://www.electrical-insulation.org/enwiki/power_factor_correction_of_induction_motor).